

X-Ray Refraction: A New Nondestructive Evaluation Method for Analysing the Interface of Composites in the Nanometerrange

Ekenhorst, D.; Hentschel, M.P.; Lange, A; Schors, J.V.
Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing, Berlin

ABSTRACT

Because of the limitations of existing failure criteria more and more research is applied to the development of damage growth models. The development and the verification of damage mechanics needs quantitative and qualitative values about the damage propagation which could be in the nanometer scale. For this purpose a new nondestructive evaluation method has been developed: X-Ray Refraction. X-Ray Refraction uses the effect of x-rays passing through the interfaces of two media with different phase velocities. Because of the good penetration of x-rays and its short wave length (below 0.2 nm) micro cracks, fibre debonding, porosity etc. can be determined in the range of the x-ray wave length. The refraction of x-rays by spherical particles (fibre surfaces) is derived and the application of x-ray refraction is applied to growth damage caused in CFRP treated at elevated temperatures and by low velocity impact at CFRP plates.

INTRODUCTION

In the past a huge number of failure criteria for composites materials has been developed and published and from the engineering point of view it becomes more and more difficult to choose the right failure criterion, especially if the engineering problem becomes more complex. Most failure criteria uses uniaxial or biaxial stress fields, while in most real situations the stress field is triaxial. Moreover especially out of plane stresses and defects like micro cracks, delaminations, porosity and fibre debonding reduce the accuracy of failure criteria. Furthermore many failure criteria suffer from the disadvantage of being applied layer by layer through the thickness of a laminate. Others are using empirical constants that have to be re-evaluated for each new geometry or lay-up.

To overcome this problem the use of damage mechanic models could eliminate the problems of using existing failure criteria. Damage mechanics are mathematical descriptions of various types of damage [1]. From such modelling the damage growth changes in laminate stiffness and strength can be evaluated and this can be used to predict failure.

The experimental verification and determination of the damage growth is still a problem in the further development of damage mechanics. This is because quantitative damage growth determination are needed for defects like fibre debonding, micro cracks, porosity down to nanometerscale.

Classical techniques to determine such damages suffer from the inherent destructive nature

like that associated with microscopy or its lack of resolution associated with radiography or ultrasonics.

To overcome this problem a new NDE method has been developed (x-ray refraction) which is sensitive in the nanometerange and which is also quantitative.

SMALL ANGLE X-RAY SCATTERING OF FIBRES

In analogy to the well known phenomenon of refraction of visible light at interfaces of transparent media like prisms and lenses, X-rays are refracted as well [2]. The essential difference to optics is the much better penetration of materials, the very small scattering angle of X-rays and a sensitivity for small structures in the nanometer range. In order to characterise heterogeneous materials like composites the refraction of X-rays at interfaces can be exploited. Fibre debonding can as well be localised by X-ray refraction topography [4].

Figure 1 demonstrates the deflection of x-rays of spherical particles. The typical scattering angle is only some minutes of arc as the index of refraction for $CuK\alpha$ -radiation (8 keV) is near $1 - 10^{-5}$. In fibres and spherical particles the deflection of X-rays occurs twice, when entering and when leaving the object (Figure 1, left). The intensity of the deflected X-rays is strongly dependent on the scattering angle. It falls down to zero at the critical angle of total reflection (Figure 1, right). A section of 10^{-3} of the fibre diameter contributes to the detectable refraction. The effect of total reflection of X-rays occurs as well at the grazing incidence angle but only 10^{-6} of the diameter is involved and therefore negligible. It might be interesting to note, that neutron refraction has been applied as well (for non-destructive analysis of ceramics) [5].

Figure 1: In fibres and spherical particles the deflection of x-rays occurs twice, when entering and when leaving the object, except for total reflection. The intensity of the refracted X-ray falls to zero at the critical angle of total reflection θ_c .

MODELLING OF X-RAY REFRACTION AT FIBRE SURFACES

From optical physics we know that light wave passing through a lens will be bend. The ratio of the sine's of the angles of incident and refracted rays with respect to the surface normal, is a constant whose magnitude depends on the phase velocity in the two media on either side of the surface. This is described by Snell's law.

$$\frac{\sin\alpha}{\sin\beta} = \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad (1)$$

where α and β are the angles of incidence and refraction, and n_1 and n_2 the refractive indices of the two media at an interface.

In case of x-rays the interaction with a surface can be described in terms of a complex dielectric function given by: $\kappa = 1 - 2\epsilon - 2i\beta$, [2].

The quantities ϵ and β are material and wavelength dependant, and account for the dispersive properties of the material and for any absorption effect [3].

$$\epsilon = \frac{Ne^2\lambda^2}{2\pi mc^2}, \quad \beta = \frac{\mu_L}{4\pi} \lambda \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of electrons, e the elementary charge, m electron mass, c velocity of light, λ the wave length and μ_L the linear absorption coefficient.

The refraction index is expressed by $n = \sqrt{\kappa}$. In case of λ far from absorption edges the absorption can be neglected ($\beta = 0$). Hence the refraction index is given by

$$n = 1 - \epsilon \quad (3)$$

and predicts an index which is less than unity. In agreement with the experimentally measured values. ϵ is in order of 10^{-5} for most materials.

In case of a ray passing from vacuum to glass with ($A = air$) $\epsilon_A = 0$ and $n_A = 1$, thus we can write

$$\frac{\sin\alpha}{\sin\beta} = \frac{n_G}{n_A} = 1 - \epsilon_G \quad (4)$$

For the fibres in reinforcing matrix however equation(4) is not appropriate. For later use we therefore define according to Snell's law

$$n_{mf} = \frac{n_f}{nm} = \frac{1 - \epsilon_f}{1 - \epsilon_m} \approx 1 - \epsilon_{mf} \quad (5)$$

where the indices m and f respectively denote matrix and fibre. With a good approximation ϵ_{mf} can be expressed by

$$\epsilon_{mf} = \epsilon_f - \epsilon_m \quad (6)$$

Initially we will examine the refraction of x-rays for a single fibre, and for that reason we will use the notation $n_2/n_1 = n = 1 - \epsilon$.

In Figure 1 is shown that two mechanisms exhibit contributing to the scattering of x-rays, refraction and total reflection. It is furthermore seen that due to symmetry the refraction angle β is identical at the front and the back therefore the change of the x-ray direction is 2θ including total refraction. Hence equation (4) can be written as

$$\sin(\alpha + \theta) = \sin \beta = (1 + \epsilon) \sin(\alpha) \quad (7)$$

THE TOTAL REFLECTION

Like light waves it is possible for x-rays to perform total reflection of the rays. Total reflection occurs when the ray does not enter the second material but i.e. reflected at the surface. The conditions for this is given when $\sin \beta = 1$ is achieved. In this case

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{1}{1 + \epsilon} \approx 1 - \epsilon; \quad \cos \alpha \approx \sqrt{2\epsilon} \quad (8)$$

This is normally written in terms of the critical angle δ which is the complement of the angle of incidence, hence

$$\sin \delta = \sqrt{2\epsilon} \quad (9)$$

It can easily be shown that the domain of angle δ at which total reflection occurs is very small compared to the domain of angles where x-rays are reflected. This is graphically shown in Figure 1.

REFRACTION OF X-RAYS

X-rays with incidence in a domain D will be reflected twice with reflection angle 2θ depending on the angle of incidence α and the index of refraction $(1 - \epsilon)$. The increment ϵ has been shown to be proportional to the wavelength λ^2 and the electron density ρ which can be described by

$$\epsilon \sim \lambda^2 \rho \quad (10)$$

The intensity distribution of refraction over the angle 2θ of one cylindrical fibre is given by [3]

$$I_R(2\theta) = \frac{I_o R}{\epsilon} \sin^3(\arctan \frac{\epsilon}{\theta}) \quad (11)$$

R is the radius of the fibre, I_o the intensity of the incident x-ray, θ is the angle of refraction and I_R is the refraction intensity without absorption,

In case of several (f) fibres R is substituted by $f * R$, and for a fibre rowing by T_r , where T_r is the thickness of the rowing in the direction of the radiation. Hence the x-ray intensity on account of the absorption is given by

$$I_A = I_0 e^{-[\alpha \mu_f + (1-\alpha) \mu_m] T_r} \quad (12)$$

where μ_m is the linear absorption coefficient of the matrix and μ_f the linear absorption coefficient of the fibres.

Combining equation 11 and 12 a good approximation of the intensity over the scattering θ for a roving is given by

$$I_R^*(\theta) = T_r I_a \frac{8\epsilon^2}{\theta^3} \quad (13)$$

For a constant angle and a given wave length and electron density, the additional refraction intensity is given by

$$I_R^* = I_R - I_A = C T_r I_A \quad (14)$$

$$C = \alpha \frac{S}{V} \quad (15)$$

Where I_R is the measured refraction signal, S the refracting surface, V the volume of the refracting material and α is a constant of apparatus.

Using reference samples with defined inner surface (S') per volume (V') the apparatus constant can be eliminated by measuring the reference refraction signal (C'). Hence we can write

$$\frac{S}{V} = C \frac{S'}{C'V'} \quad (16)$$

which is the inner surface density [ISD] cm^2/mm^3 .

EXPERIMENTAL

X-ray refractometry can be performed with conventional X-ray fine structure equipment using X-ray tubes. A line focus collimation of X-rays and the selection of the scattering angle has been performed using a conventional small angle scattering camera after Kratky. The sample can be positioned by micro drives. X-rays are registered by scintillation detectors and the intensity can be stored in accordance to sample position. Figure 2 presents the principle of x-ray refraction at fibres and the experimental set-up.

From a series of temperature ageing samples (CFRP [+45/-45]) with epoxy matrix, two examples are presented. The samples were treated at 150°C and 180°C for 10000 hours. During this treatment the matrix degrades and cracks appear in the laminate. The classical way of determining the crack density is done by microscopy at the sample edge to determine the number of cracks over a certain area. The disadvantage of this classical technique is the limited information only obtained from the edge area which could lead to an overestimation of the crack density because we know from classical laminate theory that out of plane stresses causes higher stresses at the free edge than in the bulk of the laminate.

Therefore the goal is to find a new way of describing the crack density, which includes sensitivity to nanometer cracks over the whole sample width. Cracks can be understood as

boundaries of different media (matrix/fibre and air) which have different x-ray phase velocities. These interfaces cause strong x-ray refraction whose sensitivity is determined by the x-ray wave length. The x-ray refracted intensity can be interpreted as inner surface density related to the amount of cracks.

Figure 2: Principle of X-ray refraction at fibre surfaces (right) and the set-up of two detector refraction instrument (left)

The inner surface density (ISD) is the amount of inner surfaces within a unit volume. For a quantitative interpretation the refracted intensity is compared to a) that of a perfectly bonded untreated CFRP and b) that of a loose fibre bundle which represents the half maximum possible refracted intensity.

Figure 3 shows the intensity of the refracted intensity versus the position in the sample of a a) untreated b) a treated at $150^{\circ}C$ and a c) $180^{\circ}C$ treated CFRP sample. It can be shown by Figure 4 that the crack density increases with temperature from $150^{\circ}C$ to $180^{\circ}C$ from $1.18cm^2/mm^3$ to $3.34cm^2/mm^3$, which is almost a factor of 2.5. Compared to the maximum possible crack density caused by the fibres is this 12% for CFRP 150 and 29% for CFRP 180.

Another type of defect is presented in Figure 5. In many papers a defect created by a low velocity impact is determined by its delamination area. A low resolution (1mm) x-ray refraction topography scan from a CFRP test plate (0/90) of two impacts and two paper inserts is presented in Figure 6. This topography scan gives the information which can also be observed by ultrasonic C-scan [4]. Investigating the same impact with a much higher resolution ($20\ \mu m$) shows that around the delamination area a high amount of inner surfaces are present. These surfaces are debonded fibres around the impact. This means that the real defect size of an impact is not entirely determined by the obvious delamination area. The total low velocity impact damage is described by the delamination area and the amount of inner surfaces (cracks, fibre debonding) surrounding the delamination.

REFERENCES

1. de Rouvray, Haug, Dowlatyari, Beaumont and Spearing "Advanced model development and validation for composites damage mechanics" Workshop: Design for space Applications, ESA WPP-004 Oct 1988, ESTEC, Noordwijk, The Netherlands
2. Compton, A. H. and Allison, S. "X-rays in theory and experiment" MacMillan, London 1935, p 284

3. Hentschel, M. P.; Hosemann, R.; Lange, A.; Uther, B.; Brückner, R. "Röntgenkleinwinkelbrechung an Metalldrähten, Glasfäden und hartelastischem Polypropylen" *Acta Cryst.* A43 (1987) S. 506-513
4. Harbich, K.-W. and Hentschel M.P. "Charakterisierung von Hochleistungsverbundwerkstoffen mittels Röntgenrefraktion" *GIT Fachzeitschrift für das Laboratorium* 38 (1994) pp 1324-1329
5. Hardman-Rhyne, K., Berk, N.F. and Fuller, E.R., Jr. "Micro structural characterization of ceramic materials by small angle neutron scattering techniques" *Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards* 89 (1984) 1, pp 17-34

Figure 3: The x-ray refraction intensity, showing the intensity difference over the sample position of untreated (CFRP) and temperature ageing treated CFRP (CFRP 150, CFRP 180)

Figure 4: Inner surface density over the sample position untreated (CFRP) and temperature ageing treated CFRP (CFRP 150, CFRP 180)

Figure 5: Refraction topography of the CFRP 150°C (left) and CFRP 180°C (right), showing the crack density distribution of a 5 * 5mm area

Figure 6: X-ray refraction scanning topography of a low velocity impact on CFRP (0/90) laminate. Image area 90mm², vertical resolution 1mm (left) with two impact areas (top left and bottom right) and two paper inserts simulating planar delamination. And a high resolution refraction topography of the right bottom impact, image area 20mm² vertical resolution 20µm (right)